

New Flax/Epoxy and CF/Epoxy Composite Materials for Bone Fracture Plate Applications: A Biological and Wettability Study

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1. General Introduction

Fixation of long bone fractures with clinically-available metal plates may be limited because of a mismatch between the stiffness of the metal plate and the host cortical bone [1-3]. This mismatch can result in “stress shielding”, which leads to more load transfer to the plate instead of the bone, thereby resulting in bone resorption and eventual implant loosening [2,3]. Thus, designing a fracture plate with mechanical properties close to cortical bone can reduce the negative effect of “stress shielding”. In this regard, composite materials have been suggested as an alternative to metals for manufacturing orthopaedic implants [4, 5]. These composites consist of a polymer matrix reinforced by synthetic fibers to achieve acceptable mechanical stiffness and strength [4-6]. However, their success depends on biocompatibility of both matrix and fibers [6].

With respect the matrix, epoxy is one of the most widely used polymers for orthopaedic and dentistry applications, like coating implantable devices, such as titanium and biosensors [7]. bisphenol-A [7]. Regarding the fiber, natural fibers have been investigated because of their high strength to weight ratio, high stiffness to weight ratio, low cost, low density, and their renewability and ecofriendly characteristics [8, 9]. Recently, a few studies have investigated the use of natural fibers for medical applications [8, 9, 10]. However, one of the main limitations of natural fibers is their hydrophilicity [8, 9, 11], which can be eliminated by chemical treatments or adding external layers of a hydrophobic material [2].

Due to the above-mentioned limitations of the use of natural fibers, it is important to assess the biocompatibility of natural fibers-based composites. Few investigations determined the biocompatibility of

composites containing flax fibers only for wound healing and tissue scaffolding [12, 13]. However, no studies to date have examined the cytotoxicity and wettability of 2 new composites developed by the current authors, namely, a Flax/epoxy and CF/epoxy composite materials with potential orthopaedic fracture plate applications. Therefore, as part of an ongoing program to develop a CF/flax/epoxy bone fracture plate, the purpose of this study was to assess the the cytotoxicity and wettability of Flax/epoxy and CF/epoxy composite materials in comparison to 316L stainless steel specimens obtained from a commercially-available clinical fracture plate. The current authors have previously shown that composite materials made of the same CF/flax/epoxy investigate at present have comparable mechanical stiffness (40 GPa), yet superior mechanical strength (400 MPa) [2] to that of human cortical bone (stiffness, 7–25 GPa; strength, 50–150 MPa) [14]. The authors hypothesized that the Flax/epoxy and CF/epoxy composites would demonstrate good bio-compatibility and wettability comparable to that of 316 stainless steel specimens.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Specimen Preparation

The Flax/Epoxy composite plates was manufactured using 16 layers of unidirectional (UD) Flax/Epoxy prepreg sheets (Lineo NV, Dendermonde, Belgium), with a density of 1.3 g/cm³ and a volume fraction of 58-60% which were heat-pressed for 60 min in a compression molding machine (Carver Press, Wabash, IN, USA) at 150 °C and 5 bar pressure. CF/Epoxy

specimens were manufactured with an autoclave technique using 16 layers of CF/epoxy prepreg sheets (Hexcel® Composites, Stamford, CT, USA), with a density of 1.56 g/cm³ and a volume fraction of 57%. The manufactured composite sheets were then cut with a table saw to create rectangular specimens; 15 mm long X 5 mm wide X 4 mm thick. The 316L stainless steel specimens (Zimmer, Warsaw, IN, USA) were cut to the same dimensions as the composite specimens.

2.2. Sterilization and Cell Cultures

Prior to culture, specimens were sterilized by autoclave (Heidolph, USA) using 121°C at 200 kPa for 45 min. A rat osteoblast-like cell line, URM-106 osteosarcoma (American Type Culture Collection, USA) was used, since it is widely used as a human osteoblastic model [15, 16]. Cells were grown at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere in Dulbecco Minimal Essential Medium (DMEM), supplemented with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), 2mM-glutamine, and 1% Penicillin Streptomycin (PS) at 5% CO₂ and 37°C.

2.3. Extract Preparation

Specimens were immersed in DMEM as an extracting media with an extraction medium volume to surface area ratio of 1.25 cm²/ml at 5% CO₂ and 37°C [17]. Extraction was completed over 24 hrs, at which point the extraction media was removed and centrifuged before being applied to cell cultures.

2.4. MTT Assay-Indirect Test

The cytotoxicity of composite conditioned media was assessed against URM-106 osteoblast-like cells using MTT assay in 96-well plates. Living cells can enzymatically convert the MTT salt, which result in a color change from yellow, 3-(4, 5-dimethylthiazole-2-yl)-2, 5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide, into purple formazan crystal. The number of viable cells is directly proportional to the intensity of the color produced which can be recorded by reading absorbance at 590 nm on an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay plate reader (ELISA). URM-106 cultured cells were seeded at 1×10^4 cells/ml in a 96-well plate and allowed to adhere for 24 hrs at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere, before being media aspirated. Extraction cultures were kept at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere. Control samples were URM-106 cells grown on tissue culture plastic (TCP) supplemented with complete DMEM that was not exposed to extracts. After 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs of incubation, extracts were removed and each well was treated with MTT solution at 5% CO₂ and 37°C for 4 hrs. The medium was aspirated from each well and subsequently 100 µL of Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO) was added, and the plate was shaken for 5 min before recording the optical density at 590 nm with a corrected wavelength at 690 nm. Cytotoxicity was measured as the percentage of control cell viability.

2.5. Wettability

According to ASTM standard for moisture absorption properties of polymer matrix composite materials, the water absorption test was performed by immersing the CF/epoxy and Flax/epoxy samples in a distilled water

bath at room temperature [18]. Each day for 45 days, the samples were weighed to the nearest 0.1 mg . The contact angle (CA) at the liquid-solid surface of each specimen was exactly measured using the sessile drop technique [19]. Briefly, a drop water drop from a syringe was located onto the surface of the samples and the the drops were imaged digitally by a Charged-Coupled Device Camera (CCD-Camera). From each composite materials, six specimen were tested The same wettability tests were performed on a CF/flax/epoxy composite manufactured previously [2], to study how an external layer of carbon fiber would affect the behavior of the material in absorbing moistures.

2.6. Statistical Analysis

For each of the 4 test groups in the MTT assay, 4 samples were used from which 3 measurement readings were taken. Current data are represented as mean \pm standard deviation. In order to compare the cell viability of the 4 test groups at each time period and also to compare the effect of time on a given test group, all data were combined into a single one-way ANOVA. Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference method was also used for all post hoc tests to find out exactly which pair-wise comparisons resulted in the statistical differences between test groups at the same time point. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. For wettability tests, 6 specimens were used for each group, and a similar one-way ANOVA was used for CA and water absorption results. Two-tailed post hoc power analysis was conducted to determine if there were enough specimens per test group to detect all the

statistical differences that may have been actually present.

3. Results

3.1. MTT Assay- Indirect Test Data

For each time point, comparisons between the 4 test groups are summarized (Fig. 1). After 24 hrs, viability of cells grown in CF/Epoxy, Flax/epoxy and 316L extracts was comparable for all tested groups and remained at around 100% ($p=0.364$). After 48 hrs, the viability of cells exposed to Flax/epoxy extract significantly decreased to 70% when compared to that of the TCP control ($p<0.001$). However, a reduction in cell viability exposed to CF/Epoxy extract was not significantly different from that of 316L ($p=0.897$). After 72 hrs, the viability of cells exposed to extract of all tested materials was significantly different when compared to TCP ($p<0.001$). Viability of cells grown in Flax/epoxy extract decreased significantly compared to that of 316L samples and reached 40% that of the TCP control ($p<0.001$). However, no difference observed between CF/Epoxy versus 316L ($p=0.259$). Morphology of cells at each time point is also shown (Fig. 2), which confirms the results of MTT assay. Similar to MTT results (Fig. 1), the number of viable cells stayed around 100% at 24 hrs. Although fewer cells were observed at 24 hrs compared to 48hrs and 72 hrs, this can be further explained as the number of viable cells exposed to each extract at each time point were obtained as the percentage of the control. In other words, the number of viable cells that were not exposed to extracts (i.e.

TCP) was considered 100 at each time point. Also the doubling time of UMR-106 cells is approximately 24 hrs [30], as a result fewer numbers of cells were observed at 24 hrs compared to 48hrs and 72 hrs.

For each test group, changes over time are shown (Fig. 1). Generally, the cell viability decreased with increasing incubation time for all studied extracts. As mentioned earlier, cell viability stayed around 100% for all test groups that were exposed to extracts for 24 hrs. Thus, the 24-hr mark was selected as a reference point. For Flax/epoxy, with respect to the 24-hr mark, after 48 hrs and 72 hrs of incubation time, cell viability dropped to 70% and 40%, respectively ($p<0.001$). For CF/Epoxy, with respect to the 24-hr mark, cell viability at 72 hrs significantly decreased to approximately 80% ($p<0.001$). For 316L, the level of cell viability was not significantly different at 24 hrs versus 48 hrs ($p=0.056$), but it became significantly different for 24 hrs versus 72 hrs ($p=0.008$).

3.2. Wettability Tests

The water absorption behaviour of the composites is shown (Fig.3). The maximum water uptake for CF/epoxy, Flax/epoxy, and CF/flax/epoxy composite specimens, after 45 days, reached almost 1.25 %, 17.2% and 8.3%, respectively ($p<0.001$). Although the best fit curve was logarithmic for CF/epoxy and Flax/epoxy, it was polynomial for CF/flax/epoxy with R^2 values equal to 0.90, 0.98 and 0.98, respectively (Fig.3). In addition, the CA for CF/epoxy, Flax/epoxy, and CF/flax/epoxy, in turn, was equal to $93.22^\circ \pm 1.95^\circ$, $68.07^\circ \pm 2.05^\circ$, and $83.39^\circ \pm 2.37^\circ$ ($p<0.001$).

The Flax/epoxy and the CF/flax/epoxy revealed a hydrophilic character because their CA was smaller than 90° [19, 20]. However, CF/epoxy showed a

4. Discussion

The surface of the biomaterial is the first component of an implant that comes into contact with the cells and biological fluids [21]. Thus, surface characteristics, specially the wettability, would definitely affect the material's biocompatibility. It has been long assumed that the high wettability evidenced by low CA would result in better biocompatibility for some specific applications, such as dental impression and intraocular lenses [22,23]. However, studies on blood-contacting devices and tissue engineering substrate suggest that materials with a moderate balance of hydrophilic and hydrophobic surfaces would demonstrate better biocompatibility [24]. In this study, CF/epoxy composite with the hydrophobic surface showed a better compatibility, as per the MTT assay results, compared to Flax/epoxy composite with the hydrophilic surface, which can absorb more media and release many particulates compared to other studied groups.

The difference between the viability of cells treated with Flax/epoxy and CF/epoxy may be related to the hydrophilic and hydrophobic surface of Flax/epoxy and CF/epoxy, respectively. The low CA (smaller than 90°) on Flax/epoxy composite related to the material's high surface energy to absorb moisture and water, whereas CF/epoxy composite had a hydrophobic

hydrophobic character since its CA was larger than 90° [19, 20].

surface, caused by its large CA (larger than 90°) [19, 20]. For that reason, the Flax/epoxy composite absorbed water up to 17.2% but CF/epoxy composite only absorbed water up to 1.25% (Fig.3). Therefore, the Flax/epoxy composite, due to its hydrophilic nature, may “draw” or “suck” the media from the cells and thus contributes to cell death.

The negative effect of “stress shielding” caused by high-stiffness metallic materials, can be reduced by using bone fracture plates with lower axial stiffness [1-3]. Orthopaedic plates with lower axial stiffness and sufficient bending stiffness may allow the underlying bone to carry a substantial amount of applied load and immobilize adjacent bone fragments at the fractured site, respectively [25, 26]. It was shown previously that CF/Flax/Epoxy composite materials made of the same CF /epoxy and Flax/epoxy studied at present study, yield moduli of elasticity (41.7 and 57.4 MPa) much closer to that of cortical bone (19 GPa) [27], compared to titanium (E = 110 GPa [28]) and stainless-steel plates (E = 220 GPa), with much higher moduli of elasticity, may cause less “stress shielding” effect [29]. The CF/Flax/epoxy composite has high enough ultimate flexural strength (510.6 MPa) and ultimate tensile strength (399.8 MPa) to prevent gross motion at the fracture site and carry clinical-type loads on the human femur (2.5 to 3 times body weight) [2,27], which make this material

appropriate candidate for long bone fracture plate applications.

5. Conclusion

The study evaluated a new CF/epoxy and a new Flax/epoxy composite material developed by the authors for potential use as an orthopaedic fracture plate. The hydrophilic characteristic of Flax/epoxy composite, which caused greater water absorption compared to CF/epoxy composite, may cause additional cell death. The cell viability/ proliferation rate on the CF/epoxy warrants further investigation for its potential in medical applications.

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Figures:

Fig 1. Effect of specimen extracts on the viability/proliferation rate of rat osteoblast-like cells at 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 72 hrs. Results are expressed as % of TCP control and are the mean ± SD of 4 independent experiments (Symbols (&, \$, ~, #, @, *, **, %, %%, ^, ^^, +, ++)) indicate pairwise comparisons that were statistically different (p<0.05), whereas all other comparisons were not different (p>0.05).

Fig 2. Cell morphology at 10X magnification and different time point a) 24 hrs b) 48 hrs c) 72 hrs.

Fig 3. Water absorption comparing Flax/epoxy, CF/Flax/epoxy, and CF/epoxy. Error bars are 1 standard error of the mean.